

A REVIEW OF MARKABAY JIEMURATOV'S WORK

Jamil Charshemov

Head of the Department of "General Professional and Social Humanities" of the Nukus
Branch of the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan

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Abstract. This article deeply analyzes and reveals the short life of composer Markabay Jiemuratov, his works and his symphonic poem "Ernazar Alakoz". The article also talks about other works of Markabay Jiemuratov.

Key words: composition, orchestra, symphonic poem, song, harmony.

ОБЗОР РАБОТЫ МАРКАБАЯ ДЖЕМУРАТОВА

Аннотация. В этой статье глубоко анализируется и раскрывается короткая жизнь композитора Маркабая Джемуратова, его произведения и симфоническая поэма "Ерназар Алакоз". В статье также рассказывается о других работах Марка бея Джемуратова.

Ключевые слова: композиция, оркестр, симфоническая поэма, песня, гармония.

While studying at school Markabay Jiemuratov studied works of Russian and European classical composers under the guidance of his teacher N. Mukhammeddinov. In particular, learning to play the magical works of the legendary violinist Paganini on the violin led to his sincere interest in the world of music.

A tireless passion for music led to the development of Markabay's musical and compositional technique. At that time he was noticed by writing melodies "On the mountains of Bestobe", "Missing you" etc. In particular, the song "Missing you" has recently become a love song for young people. These poems are pleasant in structure, charming and memorable, romantic in nature. Consequently, we can say that these songs are key to the transition from the typical form of a couplet to the form of a romance.

In 1969 M.Jiemuratov entered the composition department of the Tashkent State Conservatory. There he entered the preparatory courses of etiquette, studied in the class of Boris Giyenko and then moved to the class of Georgiy Mushel. Markabay Jiemuratov's enthusiasm and talent was felt by his teachers, and he began to rework folk songs and write small pieces as piano lessons. For example, he begins to write "Lullaby", "Polka", "March", "Waltz", "Fugette", "Scherzo", etc. Professor G. A. Mushel especially put a lot of effort into strengthening the future composer's other methods of music education, as well as his approach to more lyrical works.

These circumstances determined the peculiarities of Markabai Jiemuratov's compositional talent, the ways of his formation as a composer-lyricist. Talented Markabay, having taken care of this, expands his musical imagination and begins to try to record chamber-vocal music. Here it is worth noting that our composers used to compose only mass compositions, but recently they have started to promote vocal music in every possible way, drawing particular attention by its breadth of melodic diapason and power of influence.

Working on melodies, he broadened the scope of them. Old folk songs differ in their value and in that they are close to Karakalpak folk songs, especially to epics performed by bakshi, and attract special attention by the breadth of their scope and influencing power.

These signs of affinity are especially noticeable in the fixation of a number of artistic means, including the prevalence of lyrical styles, the deepening and intensification of the emotional impact of personal inner experiences, the depth and emotionality of artistic images, and finally, the breadth of the melodic flow.

M.Jiemuratov's works created with these methods are "Missing you", "Spring of Eighteen", "I hurry to you", "When I See You", "Sing me the songs of Ajiniyaz", "Loving you", "Looking at you from far", "In the field of tulips", "Moon's light on water", "Girls Singing a Song", "Golden Lake", "Song of the dawn".

One of the most important and hidden artistic means of Markabay's poems is that the text and the meaning of the poem create a structural parallelism. In fact, if the singer and the composer come together in any work, the idea and purpose of them are fully understood, and such an act is bound to be close to the people's hearts. This is one of characteristic qualities of the young composer M. Jiemuratov.

This similarity structure is felt in all his previously mentioned songs. For example, let's take "I am hurrying to you". In these couplets-romances the importance of the power of the image, its artistic diversity, the artistic diversity of each of the couplets of "My beloved is singing in the field of tulips" is equally explained in the couplet and in the title, and is equally realized in both of them.

In terms of the completeness of the composition of the poem, the number and length of artistic descriptive means and figurative comparisons give the poem a romantic and cantilena tone. In them, as in professional music, the speaker reaches a climax and gives the listener great pleasure.

Themes of youthful energy, pure love and enthusiasm feature prominently in these compositions. That is why they have become the most beloved programs of our youth. If you pay more attention to the nature of these connections, you can find all sorts of ways of parallelism (correspondence). A distinction is made between techniques of more or less ascending sequence, artistic, repetition, and compositional techniques with embroidered syllables. Taking into account the clarity, power and effectiveness of such means of artistic representation in the composer's verses, we see that Markabay paid deep attention to the expressiveness of artistic perception when writing the words of the song, and put the main compositional issues in the foreground, which forced him to pay attention to the language of poetry.

The symphonic poem "Ernazar Alakoz".

One of M.Jiemuratov's literary achievements was the story of the heroism of the legendary hero of the Karakalpak man Ernazar Alakoz, a symphonic poem about the hero of his freedom "Ernazar Alakoz".

The main content of the symphonic poem is the struggle of the Karakalpak people and the heroism of the national hero Ernazar Alakoz in this struggle, the composer expressed in different ways in his work. These symphonic styles are revealed through tension, rhythmic and harmonic juxtapositions, and pleasing coloration. The symphonic poem is written in the form of a one-part sonata allegro. The sad content of the cello and double bass instruments in its opening section is given in a lower register, and it sounds weak, as if heralding a heavy, dangerous event in the future performance. On the basis of this content, beginning with the first measure of the symphony, the story of the former misfortunes of the people is told.

The composer describes his main purpose, the plot of the work, a touching image from the chords played in unison. It is as if he is presenting a spark of hope, of faith in the future, based on a short theme in lyrical form. After this, between intervals of one quarter and one fifth, the orchestra plays fragments explaining the approaching event and stories about the enemy's attack, which are played intermittently by the trumpets. At the end, as if to explain the approach of the enemy, a single heavy chord is played throughout the orchestra, and after a brief pause the main exposition section of the symphony begins. In this section, the composer attempts to reveal the programmatic meaning he has chosen, the historical event, and the compositional play, which have an inimitable unity of juxtaposition, harmonic, and thematic unity. The introduction part, that is, in the initial movement, as in all compositional sonatas develop around two contents. The main content is active, playful, and dynamic, with violins from a group of narrow instruments playing in it. This content with its characteristic, twists and turns is played fast like fugue. The instruments of bassoon, clarinet, and double bass complement this content and enhance their harmony. The auxiliary theme creates a perfect contrast.

Auxiliary content is beautiful in aural character, intonation, and color, with a vivid image and a strong impression. In particular, this content is provided by the gavotte, which must be beautiful, pleasing, and somehow beautiful in tone. This theme would then be played on other instruments, sometimes extended, sometimes shortened. In doing so, the composer was adept at using all sorts of imitation techniques, pizzicato (interruption of sound), and polyphony techniques used in the orchestra. The composer then begins to show the most urgent content of his thought in the part of the work that is saturated with dynamic and dramatic situations. In this part, the elements of drama are Ernazar Alakoz' confrontation with his opponent, the struggle between them and the actions that increase the content of the symphony.

In the performance of Ernazar Alakoz symphony, the composer uses all kinds of compositional and individual composition techniques, and the action and power of his sound reveal his work under the influence of brief quarto-quint intervals, the famous moving trombone and clarinet motif. Thus, in this section, after each theme alternates in a different polyphonic manner, the final reprise section of the work begins after a brief pause. This section describes the torment of the people, the invasion of the Khan of Khiva, and the heat of war under the command of Ernazar Alakoz, where he heroically dies. Through the wistful sounds of the orchestra one can hear the groaning of the people. In this section, the composer depicts two leitmotif themes: the enemy theme and the Ernazar Alakoz theme. In praising the enemy theme, he gives unstated chromatic motifs, while in Ernazar Alakoz's theme his heroic help is praised with a solemn theme.

The enemy theme is developed canonically, showing the inexorable movement of their armies, and in the orchestra, as if constantly increasing their melodic meaning, all instruments of all stripes continue the melodic line without stopping. In the development of the symphony on the content of the event, the composer was able to demonstrate his symphonic style with strong dramatic elements, seventh chords, chromatism, and active melodic flows. At the end of the work, a joyful panphoric theme is played live by the entire orchestra. The work ends with the triumph and celebration of the people. "Ernazar Alakoz" by the young composer M. Jiemuratov was able to make great strides in mastering the compositional and symphonic genre.

Apart from the fact that this symphony is a great contribution to the formation and development of professional music genre in Karakalpakstan, it is based on original titles without quoting folk names. Symphony “Ernazar Alakoz” was performed in 1975 in Tashkent at the concert hall "Bahar" under the guidance of young composers performed by a large symphony orchestra and was highly appreciated.

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